

SCIENTIFIC VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS ON EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article contains opinions about the scientific-theoretical concepts and views of Eastern thinkers on education. There were also discussions about children's upbringing in Islam and the pedagogical views of thinkers in their creative activities.

Key words: education, manners, humanitarianism, universal human values, national value, national thinking, Islamic culture, pedagogical activity.

Our nation has a rich heritage of education created during its long history. In addition, he has accumulated a unique experience of forming universal human qualities such as humanity, humility, hard work, friendship, faith, kindness, and decency in generations. We know that spiritual and moral qualities never arise by themselves, but there is a real source of their origin, the reasons that cause them and the forces that move them. After all, any moral rules arise as a result of certain historical necessity and develop on the basis of certain laws. It should be emphasized that the views of Eastern thinkers on education had a great influence on the formation of this experience.

Education is the duty of parents and the right of children. The word "Tarbiya" is derived from the Arabic verb "robba" and means to grow, to increase, to follow, to lead and to reform. Muslim scholars defined "education" in several different ways. For example, Imam Bayzavi describes it as follows: Education is to gradually bring something to perfection. "Roghib Asfikhani defines education as follows:" Education is to bring something from one state to another and bring it to the point of completeness. One of the meanings of education is to grow the religious, intellectual and moral powers of a person with harmony and balance. In Islam, raising children is the most responsible and lasting duty of parents. Other duties end by doing some work or spending property. But the responsibility of upbringing will continue. In fact, parents' true gratitude for the blessing of their children comes out by fulfilling the responsibility of upbringing with honor¹.

It would not be an exaggeration to say that Islam started the issue of etiquette in the history of mankind. In Islam, everything in a person's life has its own etiquette. It is not an exaggeration to say that the basis and majority of works on etiquette in the world are written by representatives of Islamic nations². The views and ideas advanced by Eastern thinkers in ancient times continue to provide spiritual nourishment to the minds and hearts of young people as an important educational source.

The peoples of Central Asia, with a long and rich history, have created and improved their rich heritage of education, educating young people in the spirit of universal human qualities such as humanity, science, kindness, hard work, friendship to people and nature, and

¹ Sheikh Mukhammad Sadik Mukhammad Yusuf. "Baxtiyor oila". T.: "Hilal-Nashr". 2013 y 339-340 pp.

² Sheikh Mukhammad Sadik Mukhammad Yusuf. "Baxtiyor oila". T.: "Hilal-Nashr". 2013 y 342 p.

generosity. Have come In fact, the priceless cultural heritage left by our ancestors is the core of our national spirituality. Therefore, it is appropriate to use it widely for the education and upbringing of our youth today. Because, "The heritage left by our ancestors is a source of strength and dedication not only for the past, but also for the future of our nation"³. Every nation has traditions related to education, which serve as the basis for the development of pedagogical thinking and express ideas and views about child education. As we said above, every parent wants their children to become perfect human beings, they think that their children will have the dreams and hopes that they have not been able to achieve. They rejoice at every achievement of the children and worry about their defeat. Seeing their children happy is the happiest moment for them. For this, they spend all their energy on them.

Witness how in the past our great scholars taught high-level spirituality and morals, expressed their views on the Motherland, people's perspective, prosperous life, honest work, scientific development, human work, and reasonable attitude to the environment. let's

Khoja Ahmed Yassavi can be included in the list of such eternal scholars. It is clear from the conducted researches that Khoja Ahmed Yassavi, with his spiritual and moral views, was able to make an incomparable contribution to the science of pedagogy even today. "According to Khoja Ahmed Yassavi's point of view, deceit and concealment of sins are betrayal of others. With these thoughts, Khoja Ahmed Yassavi promotes truthfulness, honesty, and self-reliance. He puts forward the idea that a person who has worked hard will be patient, resilient, and willful. Vigilance motivates a person to take active action. The wisdom of Khoja Ahmed Yassavi encourages the reader to be vigilant, to be active, to avoid conspiracies and corruption"⁴. That is why it is advisable to use them widely in the educational process.

Another great scholar is Burkhaniddi Marginani. In Burkhaniddiy Marginani's views on moral and legal education, the ideas of religion, faith, conscience, duty, and humanity served as the main means of comprehensive and harmonious development of the individual. From this point of view, freedom, humanitarianism, hard work, faith, honesty, moral purity, justice, fraternity, knowledge, and independent thinking are the main features of Burkhaniddiy Marginani's views on moral and legal education, a major representative of Islamic teachings who lived in the 21st century occupies the rin⁵. Scientist Marginani made a significant contribution to the development of the spirituality of our people, the development of the culture of the Muslim world, and the development of social and pedagogical thought with his ethical and legal views.

Consider it a legacy to teach your child manners and skills. Whether you teach him manners or not, life's hardships will teach him. They say that if the parents do not educate them, they educate them day and night⁶. In the 44-chapter work "Nightmare" by Kaykovus, the tasks and duties of parents in raising children, the child's attitude towards parents, valuing them, the manners of dealing between people, their mutual moral relations, avoiding bad habits such as insults and rudeness In addition to the necessity, emphasis is placed on moral issues such as paying serious attention to child's upbringing and the great responsibility of parents for their future.

³ A. Khaydarov. Human perfection and national-spiritual values. T.: Editor, 2008 y.

⁴ M. Khajiyeva. Spiritual and educational views of Khoja Ahmed Yassavi. Abstract. T.: 2004

⁵ M. Shokhadjyaev. Burkhaniddin Marginani's views on moral and legal education. Abstract. Year: 2006

⁶ M. Hamdamova. The foundations of spirituality. T.: "Science and technology". 2008.

Knowledge of educational methods and means of inculcating the ideas, views, and ideas of Eastern thinkers in the creative activity of Eastern thinkers into the minds of the young generation, and their correct use in life is one of the important features of the pedagogical skills of teachers in the educational process. In recent years, the interest in the topic of ethics has increased significantly. Because after we gained national independence, the need to study our historical and cultural heritage increased, and the interest of our people to know the moral ideas in the content of our national, religious and spiritual values is increasing.

The first condition for fundamentally changing the humanistic direction of the educational system and raising it to the level of modern requirements is to approach it as a whole system and work accordingly.

Cultivation of high moral qualities in the young generation, formation of national ideology, respect for our rich cultural heritage, historical traditions, universal human values, love for the Motherland, loyalty to the ideas of independence is the decisive factor of all the reforms implemented in our country. The main goal of our policy in the field of spirituality is to ensure people's deep understanding of their identity, the value of independence, the expansion and improvement of national thinking, the awakening of the spirit of historical freedom and independence.

The famous Uzbek pedagogue Abdulla Avloni wrote that "Education is a matter of life or death for us, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster".

According to Mashaikh, "the happiness of every nation, the peace and happiness of states depends on the good education of the youth"⁷.

A. Avloni's work "Turkish culture and morals" was taught as a textbook for education and moral education in the upper classes of new method schools. While deeply studying the work of A. Avloni, we found that in that period, they used universal and religious values, folklore, verses of the Qur'an, hadiths, as well as the wise words of our great scholars as much as possible in teaching students in schools. We will see. For example, in the topic of "Patience" which is part of "Good manners": "Patience is a great virtue for people, and His Majesty praises those who are patient." In Shariat Islam, it is obligatory to be patient with the calamity and punishment that came from the side of Mr. Haq. One of the hadiths mentioned in this regard says that the meaning of sharif is "knowledge is the protector of believers, the patron of faith, the evidence of intelligence, the source of good deeds, the source of kindness, the bearer of forgiveness, and the conscience of the governor of patience." Arabs say "assabru miftahul-falah" - patience is the key to happiness. Today's need to scientifically and theoretically develop the national pedagogical and methodological foundations of using national values in the spiritual and moral upbringing of children in the family and finding optimal ways to effectively solve it remains one of the main problems.

Therefore, raising a child in the family is a problem of national importance. For this reason, the demand of any society for the family and the upbringing of children in the family increases. At the same time, the role of the state and parents in raising children and increasing the responsibility of children to their parents will increase.

As the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I. Karimov, said, "These words of our great enlightened grandfather were as important and relevant for our nation at the beginning

⁷ M. Hamdamova. The foundations of spirituality. T.: "Science and technology". 2008

of our century, they are as important for us now, if not even more so. and acquires urgent importance".

"It is necessary to pay attention to the roots of our national culture and spiritual wealth of the people. This treasure has been accumulated over centuries. It has passed the tests of history. He helped people in difficult times. Our task is to preserve this treasure like the apple of our eye and enrich it further"⁸. This idea, which is of fundamental importance for our national development, is also important for scientific research on art.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized the education of young people: "We should educate our children ourselves, not leave them in the hands of others. For this, we need to talk more with our youth, listen to their hearts, understand their pain, and give practical help to solve their problems. In carrying out these tasks, we rely on our national traditions formed over the centuries, the rich heritage of our ancestors." We consider it our primary task to improve the activities of all links of the education and training system based on today's requirements. When talking about the education of the young generation, I would very much like that each of us, especially our sons and daughters who are coming into life, follow these thoughts of our grandfather Abdurauf Fitrat. Here is what our great ancestors wrote: "A nation should move towards a specific goal, become a state, be happy and gain respect, become a world lover, or become weak and be humiliated, bear the burden of misfortune, etc. "It depends on the education they received from their parents since childhood, that they are neglected, subordinated to others, and slaves and captives"⁹.

In turn, education begins with the family, we teach our children happiness, maturity, success, becoming a great person, and their spiritual fortress, which ensures the eternity of life and the continuity of generations. As we want to see the strength of our family, it means that it is important to pay attention to all types of education in raising our children in the family to be healthy and well-rounded in all respects. The place and role of the rich spiritual heritage left by our ancestors in the system of all-round development of the young generation has its own characteristics and manifestations. "Indeed, the education system should pay special attention to the possibilities of studying the educational values created by the ancestors. It is of great practical importance to study and analyze the works of Eastern thinkers, to research their creativity and views on education from a pedagogical point of view"¹⁰. In their works, they expressed their views on personal spirituality, the creation of high standards of morality in a person, family, marriage, raising children, making a living with honest work, and being reasonable in relation to the environment. Thus, the issues of man and his upbringing, thinkers and scholars of the East in their works glorify man's acquisition of knowledge, skill, high spiritual and moral qualities and invite everyone to acquire such qualities. No external force, idea or ideology can influence a generation that is spiritually high, has mastered modern science, and has inherited the rich spiritual heritage of our ancestors. The people who brought up such a generation have bright prospects and a great future.

⁸ I. Karimov. High spirituality is an inexhaustible power. T.: Ma'naviyat, 2008.

⁹ Sh. Mirziyoyev. His speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Year: 2016

¹⁰ Z.B. Jalilov. Didactic methods of studying the heritage of Eastern thinkers. Journal of modern education. 2017, No. 5.

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